

Size matters! On the implications of increasing the size of research grants

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Introduction

In recent years, growing attention has been placed on inequality in science. While the science system has always been characterised by a high degree of stratification (Price, 1963; Merton, 1968; Cole and Cole, 1973), recent studies indicate a strengthening of trends towards concentration of resources, rewards and recognition (Ma et al., 2015; Mongeon et al., 2016; Aagaard et al., 2020; Katz and Matter, 2020; Nielsen and Andersen, 2021). Developments over time, with increased reliance on competitive funding and declining success rates, can impact researchers' strategies for conducting research and obtaining funding (see Laudel 2022 in this Handbook). Competition is thus undergoing change along with funding conditions, where funding practices also act to shape understandings of competition (see Arora-Jonsson et al. 2022 in this Handbook).

Recent studies document an intensification in funding inequality and concentration in global science (see e.g. Lariviere, 2010; Bol et al., 2018; Katz and Matter, 2020). Policies play a key role in these developments, particularly through the design of funding instruments, where a focus on larger research grants can contribute to resource concentration. The distribution of funding has repercussions for the science system at all levels, from individual researchers to institutions, regions, and disciplines (e.g., Fortin and Currie 2013, Bol et al. 2018; Madsen and Aagaard 2020). This raises issues concerning the consequences of increased concentration of research funding.

Motivated by this recent surge in studies addressing the concentration of funding and its consequences, this chapter will explore how the trends, rationales and implications of increases in the size of grants have developed in recent years. The purpose of the chapter is to provide an overview of the potential positive and negative impacts of increases in the size of research funding and existing evidence on the role of size. With further evidence, the chapter extends an earlier paper (Bloch and Sørensen, 2015), in which we examined the role of size in competitive research funding for individual and project grants. First, we examine the potential implications of trends towards increasing grant sizes and larger grant forms. Next, we synthesize the rationales behind these trends and discuss the implications of more recent developments. Finally, we take a closer look at recent empirical examples of increases in the average size of grants. Government R&D programs are very diverse and complex, with many steps from policy to instruments, and with a variety of objectives (see also Reale et al., 2022 in this Handbook). This complexity is also visible in the plethora of different funding configurations of researchers. In this Handbook, Thomas and Ramos-Vielba (2022) explore how research and impacts are influenced by the interplay of funding strands among collaborative researchers.

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Despite a general lack of accessible data on developments in the size of grants across countries, Bloch and Sørensen (2015) found several indications of increases in funding size, but also cases where increases had not taken place. Based on a review of the literature, we identified a number of rationales behind larger grant forms, spanning from large individual or project grants to research centres. These included economies of scale in research and redistribution of resources towards top researchers as a means to increase scientific productivity and the likelihood of fostering pathbreaking research. However, these rationales should be contrasted with potential negative effects of increases in the size of grants, and the concentration of funding among a smaller number of researchers.

In recent years, the issue of funding concentration and its implications has received growing attention with results indicating that concentration and inequality in research is intensifying (Aagaard et al., 2020; Nielsen and Andersen, 2021, Bol et al., 2018; Petersen and Penner, 2014; Madsen and Aagaard, 2020). The possible ramifications of such patterns can be particularly severe for early career researchers (see e.g. Melkers and Kreth, 2022 in this Handbook on the relation between research funding and careers).

Research grants can take on many forms. In this chapter we focus on three stylized forms. The first is standard research project grants, which typically can range from 100,000 to 300,000 USD. The second is larger grant forms, in particular individual grants with larger amounts and often longer durations. The third form is research centre grants.

The chapter is structured in the following way. *First*, we examine international *trends* towards increased funding sizes. We look at empirical examples of developments in the average size of existing grants - from a range of different countries - as well as shifts in the allocation of external funding to larger grant forms. Our focus is on individual and project grants or centre grants, as opposed to block grants to universities. *Second*, we look at the *rationales* behind more recent developments and survey the literature from before and after 2015 where our original paper was published. We present the arguments pro et contra increased grant sizes and subsume arguments under seven overall but closely related categories: Efficiency/productivity, Administration, Excellence, Matthew-effects, Socioeconomic impact, Epistemic impact, and Equity. *Third*, we review evidence on the *impact* of increased funding sizes. *Finally*, we offer a brief conclusion.

Trends towards increased funding sizes and larger grant forms

Research funding systems have undergone major changes in the last decades. Worldwide there has been a shift away from a national trust-based system of funding towards a more performance-based system. Within the new performance-based system, Sörlin (2007, p. 426) points to a number contemporary trends, such as increased project-based funding, new laws for tax deductible contributions towards university research, and the expanding role of research in industry and broader society, that have fuelled the rise of academic superstars and a resulting 'winner takes all' trend in funding. A further potential implication of these trends is a concentration of funding in larger project grants and other, larger grant forms, such as large individual fellowships or research centres, partly at the expense of individual and smaller grants.

Our previous study (Bloch and Sørensen, 2015) was complicated by data limitations on basic grant characteristics such as average grant size. However, we generally found a trend towards significant increases in the size of grants in many countries, though with notable exceptions. For this chapter, we have collected additional data on funding and grant sizes across a range of funding organisations in a number of countries. Our analysis shows that the trend still exists in a number of countries, with continued increases in grant sizes

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in, for example, Denmark, Switzerland and the UK. However, average funding sizes have remained at more stable levels for many other countries and funding organisations over the past decade.

The development of the research funding system in Denmark provides an illustrative example of the trend towards increases in grant sizes. Over the course of the past two-three decades, the Danish funding system has experienced significant increases in larger grant forms, such as e.g. centres of excellence funded by the Danish National Research Foundation, along with a general increase in the size of individual project grants. For the period 2015-2020, the average size of centre grants from the Danish National Research Foundation was around 62.5 million DKK (approx. 10 million USD). In 2001, 65% of all project grants from the Council for Independent Research were below 1 million DKK (approx. 170,000 USD), while 19% of grants were above 1.5 million DKK (approx. 260,000 USD) (Bloch et al., 2011). In 2009, the share of small grants for less than 1 million DKK had dropped to 16%, while the share of project grants for more than 1.5 million DKK had increased to 70%. In the period 2001-2019, the average size of project grants had increased from 1.0 to 3.2 million DKK, an increase of 313% (237% in real terms). One consequence of this development has been that the success rate dropped from 28% in 2001 to 12% in 2009. Since then, it has remained relatively low and was at 15% in 2019.

When examining the six most prominent grant types from the Norwegian Research Council, we found that the average grant size has increased by 48% from 2011-2020 (from 1.47 million NOK to 2.18 million NOK).ⁱ Average grant sizes have also increased at the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF). Grants at the SNSF are grouped into four categories (Projects, Careers, Programmes and Infrastructure), and all types have increased in average size during the period from 2005-2020. For example, the average grant size for Projects increased from 238,000 CHF in 2005 to 534,000 CHF in 2020ⁱⁱ.

Ma et al. (2015) study developments in the distribution of research funding from the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) over a period from 1985-2013. They find large increases in the total amount of grant money available in the system and in the number of grants allocated. Moreover, they find a substantial increase in the average size of grants during the period studied (from around 200,000 GBP to more than 600,000 GBP).

At the National Science Foundation (NSF) in the US there was a 41% increase (in current dollars) from 2000 to 2005 in the annual mean award size provided by the NSF, from \$101,200 to \$142,600 per year (NSF 2007, pp. 4-5) This increase in the size of awards was motivated by the wish to "... increase productivity by minimizing the time PIs (principle investigators) would spend writing multiple proposals and managing administrative tasks, providing increased stability for supporting graduate students, and facilitating collaborations to address particularly complex issues" (NSF, 2007, p. 5). However, in more recent years, average grants sizes at the NSF have remained at a stable level, with increases similar to inflation rates. From 2012 to 2022, average grant sizes rose by 9% from 164,700 USD to 179,900 USDⁱⁱⁱ.

If we turn to the National Institutes of Health in the US (NIH), the average grant size has increased by 15% in nominal terms during the period from 2014-2020^{iv}, which is similar to the increase in prices (the GDP deflator index for the USA increased by around 11% over the same period). The NIH also funds larger research centres, though funding devoted to these centres has decreased in relative terms. In all, the NIH awarded 8.3 times more funding for individual research projects than research centres in 1995, increasing to 10.9 in 2017^v.

In Bloch and Sørensen (2015), we found that grant sizes for independent research projects (Discovery Projects) from the Australian Research Council (ARC) had not increased in recent years, though new and larger funding instruments had been introduced. These include Centres of Excellence schemes and the Future

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Fellowship funding programs, which were introduced in 2008 to attract and maintain top researchers in Australia. The average size of these new and larger funding constructions was around double the size of that for Discovery Project grants and accounted for around 15% of total ARC grant funding in 2011. Funding sizes have generally remained similar in the more recent period from 2013-2020. Average sizes of the three grant types (Discovery project, Future Fellowships and Centres of Excellence) have more or less followed inflation rates, though the share of overall funding devoted to Future Fellowships declined by 40% from 2013-2020^{vi}.

In Japan, Shibayama (2011) finds that a shift took place during the period from 1976-2005, from small grants (< 10 million JPY) to large grants (>100 million JPY). In 1976-80, 66% of funding went to small grants and none to large grants, while shares of small grants fell to 32% in 2001-05 and up to around 20% for large grants. However, the average size of smaller project grants fell from 2005 to 2011.

Excellence initiatives have been launched in a number of countries, in some cases taking up a fair share of total public research funds. In the Nordic countries relatively comprehensive Centre of Excellence (CoE) schemes have been introduced in Denmark, Finland, Norway, and Sweden over the past 20 years (Aksnes et al., 2012). In Germany, Excellence Initiatives were launched in 2005, with a budget of €1.9 billion (\$2.5 billion) (DFG, 2013). Here, 10.2% of the total budget or 747.5 million EUR (977 million USD) was spent on Clusters of Excellence funding from 2008-2010. This share has remained fairly constant from 2010-2020. The Excellence initiative led to an increase in the relative share of funding devoted to larger grant forms. The share of individual research grants went down from 39.9% in the period 1999-2001 to 28.7% in the period from 2008 to 2010 (DFG, 2003, p. 27; DFG, 2012, p. 37). In the period since 2010, the share of funding devoted to individual research grants has risen to around 33% in 2019^{vii}.

Rationales for and against increased grant sizes

As was the case in 2015 (Bloch and Sørensen, 2015), the evidence based on the examples provided in the previous section is mixed. While an increase in the size of standard research project grants can be documented for a number of national science systems, the picture is not uniform in all the countries examined. As evidenced, increasing emphasis has in more recent decades been placed on much larger grant forms, such as Centres of Excellence. In the following, we explore in detail the rationales for and against such increases in funding size and subsume arguments under seven analytical categories: *Efficiency/Productivity, Administration, Excellence, Matthew effects, Socioeconomic impact, Epistemic effects, and Equity*.

While we for purposes of clarity, view it as helpful to present these seven types of implications as analytically separate, they are in reality intricately intertwined. For example, arguments tied to ‘administrative costs’ are closely connected to ‘efficiency and productivity’. Similarly, ‘excellence’-related arguments and arguments tied to social mechanisms such as that of ‘the Matthew effect’ also share common traits. For all seven categories, an overview of the arguments for and against increased grant sizes are shown in table 1. For the most part, these arguments are relevant for all three grant forms considered here (i.e. project grants, large individual grants and centre grants), though some arguments are tied to centre grants specifically.

Table 1: Rationales behind increased grant sizes

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Topics	Arguments in favour of increased grant sizes	Arguments against increased grant sizes
Efficiency/Productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economies of scale: Scale return in performance/productivity with an increase in grant size Optimal use of resources – avoiding dilution of resources Critical mass in terms of pooling of intellectual capacity, equipment and research infrastructure "Bigger is better": Grants and research units should be large in order to increase productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diseconomies of scale: Decreasing returns to research with an increase in grant size Decreasing marginal returns: Grants above a certain size result in diminishing marginal returns measured as scientific production and impact Focus on achieving critical mass has been excessive resulting in artificially large research grants, projects, teams and consortia Excess size of research grants leading to fragmentation and problems with coordination within large research groups and consortia Productivity and performance can be enhanced via support for smaller and medium-sized grants
Administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lower assessment costs and smaller administrative burden Allocation of funding in smaller grants requires extra scrutiny, is more costly and adds to the administrative burden 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Centres</i>: Excess size of research projects may lead to cumbersome levels of administration, coordination and problems with management within large teams, centres and consortia <i>Centres</i>: May turn good scientists into 'science managers' using most of their time on administration
Excellence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large-scale funding will maximize scientific impact and the likelihood of making new discoveries Resource stability that can facilitate autonomy, the pursuit of novel ideas, and riskier research Excellence schemes are expected to generate critical mass, the pooling of resources and expertise, facilitate interdisciplinarity, research training and international visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spreading research resources across many scientists through smaller grants may result in more value for money in terms of high-impact articles <i>Centres</i>: The system still incentivizes centre grant recipients to apply for further funds, which in turn puts pressure on other non-grant holding researchers and the system as a whole
Matthew effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Larger grants intensify and accelerate the concentration of research resources on successful groups and scientists Social mechanisms in science and funding policies act to limit too unequal distributions of funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Winning of an early career grant – and not merit in itself - improves the chances of later funding and career success. Large grants magnify this process Failure to win an early career grant will diminish chances of getting funding at a later stage and even discourage future participation in funding competitions

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Socioeconomic impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Centres</i>: Large scale funding directly or indirectly promotes industry-science collaboration, thereby strengthening the impact of research on innovation and international competitiveness • <i>Centres</i>: By building strong research centres within areas deemed of strategic economic importance, research is directed towards economic goals and enhances the quality of research within selected areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Little evidence for increased scientific productivity through concentration of resources in larger grants • Consortium and centre grants can get too big leading to decreasing productivity
Epistemic effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitates research capacity and stimulates scientific development and advances • <i>Centres and large individual grants</i>: Large-scale funding schemes such as centres of excellence or large individual grants allow for resource availability, stability and flexibility to pursue 'high-risk/high-gain research' 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More grantees will increase the number of experiments and thereby the likelihood of scientific breakthroughs • Increasing the number of grant holders reduces the risk of accumulated failure and provides better conditions for risk-taking • Increasing the number of grant holders and funded areas increases the diversity of fields of research and the range of opportunities available to students and researchers
Equity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding should follow performance – the best performers should have more and larger grants • Spreading funding in smaller grants and on more researchers leads to the dilution of resources and funding bodies renouncing their control over the course of science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for more fair distribution of resources among qualified researchers, through more and smaller grants

Efficiency/Productivity

Under the broad category of Efficiency and Productivity, we find the argument that an increase in the size of research grants allows for the critical mass necessary to promote and achieve scientific excellence. According to this logic of argumentation, scientific production, impact and performance is believed to scale with an increase in the size of research grants (Bonaccorsi and Daraio, 2005; Bloch and Sørensen, 2015; Bloch et al., 2016; Hellström et al., 2017). Moreover, large grants are also thought to allow for the creation of critical mass in terms of equipment, infrastructure, intellectual capacity and expertise that can enhance research performance (Breschi and Malerba, 2011; Bloch et al., 2016; Aagaard et al., 2020). A commonly held notion here is that bigger is simply better (Bonaccorsi and Daraio, 2005). According to this strand of argumentation, funding should be distributed in large grants to avoid the dilution of resources, optimise the use of productive resources and in turn increase productivity (von Tunzelmann, 2003; Bonaccorsi and Daraio, 2005; Hicks and Katz, 2011; Vaesen and Katzav, 2017).

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However, as found in the literature, several contributions suggest that an increase in the size of research funding may in fact lead to diseconomies of scale (Johnston, 1994; von Tunzelmann et al., 2003; Bloch et al., 2016). Several studies find that there may be economies of scale for grants up until a certain threshold level after which decreasing returns set in (Bonaccorsi and Daraio, 2005; Nag et al., 2013; Bloch et al., 2016). Similarly, studies point to decreasing marginal returns – a stagnation in the productivity and citation impact of research – with grants above a certain level (Breschi and Malerba, 2011; Berg, 2012; Fortin and Currie, 2013; Bloch and Sørensen, 2015; Doyle et al., 2015; Lorsch, 2015; Bloch et al., 2016; Mongeon et al., 2016; Wahls, 2018a, 2018b). As Breschi and Malerba (2011) remark, one consequence of the excessive focus, in recent years, on achieving critical mass has been the formation of 'too large' projects and research consortia as well as the artificial enlargement of partnerships well beyond optimal levels of efficiency and productivity.

A number of empirical studies suggest that spreading out grants on more researchers at moderate funding levels is a better funding strategy, on average yielding more high-impact articles than handing out big grants to a lower number of researchers (Lorsch, 2015; Fortin and Currie, 2013; Mongeon, 2016). Another central efficiency-related argument in favour of resource dispersal is that the excess size of research projects and grants can lead to fragmentation and problems with coordination within large research teams and consortia (Alberts, 1985; Breschi and Malerba, 2011; Nag et al., 2013).

Administration

Connected to discussions of efficiency and productivity are also arguments related to administration and bureaucracy. Here, a key argument for distributing funding in fewer and bigger grant portions is the smaller administrative burden and assessment costs per funded unit (Johnston, 1994; Berg, 2012; Dimke et al., 2019). Berg (2012) describes how policies in the NIH aimed at capping funding per principal investigator and reduce resource concentration met criticism for adding to the administrative burden. According to the critique, the allocation of funding in smaller grants would require extra scrutiny and additional resources for lengthy peer-review evaluation procedures.

On the other hand, a key argument against resource concentration is that excess size of consortium and network grants can lead to cumbersome levels of administration, coordination and problems with management of partners (Alberts, 1985; Breschi and Malerba, 2011; Nag et al., 2013; Kimble et al., 2015). Alberts (1985) early on pointed out that concentration of funding may turn group leaders in big research teams into 'science managers' who spend nearly all their time on grant writing, science administration, and organizational matters, leaving little time for doing actual research and mentoring students and junior staff (see also Kimble et al., 2015).

Excellence

While the main rationale for the concentration of funding for many years has centred around achieving benefits related to critical mass and economies of scale (Johnston, 1994), focus has in more recent decades shifted towards excellence (Sørensen et al., 2016) and the concentration of funding among top researchers, both to increase production of high-quality research and to enhance conditions for the generation of scientific breakthroughs. Here, the main rationale is that the best researchers are the most productive, with

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the greatest potential to produce high-quality research and groundbreaking results (Hicks and Katz, 2011). Hence, the most efficient allocation of resources is to provide the very best with optimal material conditions for conducting research.

The increasing attention on excellence has globally resulted in a number of excellence funding schemes, primarily aimed at providing financial support for the setting up of so-called Centres of Excellence. If we consider the rationales for investing in large-scale centres of excellence (CoE schemes), the arguments revolve around the maximization of productivity, scientific impact, and providing optimal conditions for making new discoveries (Ida and Fukuzawa, 2013; Bloch et al., 2016). Another argument in favour of CoE schemes is that large-scale centre grants provide researchers with resource stability in terms of long-term generous funding that can facilitate autonomy, the pursuit of novel ideas, and riskier research (Hellström et al., 2017).

Among the arguments against the 'excellence'-agenda in science, and in line with the rationale that resource concentration may lead to inefficiencies of scale, Breschi and Malerba (2011) suggest that sustaining excellence may be more difficult with an increase in the size of projects and consortia. In other words, funding strategies targeting diversity, i.e., spreading research resources on many smaller grants and scientists, is according to this line of reasoning expected to yield more value for money in terms of high-impact articles, than pursuing funding policies aimed at achieving excellence by way of concentrating resources among the few (Fortin and Currie, 2013). Finally, while excellence schemes were initially put in place to free the most capable researchers from the arduous task of writing grant applications, the system still incentivizes centre grant recipients to apply for further funds, which in turn puts pressure on other non-grant holding researchers and the system as a whole (Sandström et al., 2010).

Matthew effects

Scientific productivity and access to research resources is unevenly distributed among researchers (Stephan, 1996; Hicks and Katz, 2011). While some of these dissimilarities undoubtedly have to do with individual level variations in talent, effort and efficiency, differences in productivity and achievement cannot solely be explained by ability, hard work and motivation, but must also be understood as 'cumulative advantage' and the ability to leverage past successes (Stephan, 1996). As a process of social selection, the Matthew effect intensifies and accelerates the concentration of research resources on successful groups and scientists (Merton, 1968; Franssen and de Rijcke, 2019; Katz and Matter, 2020). However, it is suggested that there are limits to cumulative advantage and that various social mechanisms in science act to limit too unequal distributions of funding (Bloch et al., 2016). Moreover, policies put in place by funding agencies such as NIH that try to reduce funding for well-off investigators seem to suggest that reverse Matthew effects might work to curb tendencies toward uncontrolled resource concentration (Berg, 2012).

There are however undeniable and well-documented negative effects of the Matthew effect, as it sets in motion processes of cumulative advantage where the winning of an early career grant significantly improves the chances of later funding and career success, while nonwinners do not reap the same career benefits (Bol et al., 2018). Whereas early funding success will promote continued participation in the competition for funding, early career failure to win a grant will discourage future participation in funding competitions (Bol et al., 2018, p. 4887). The handing out of larger grants will magnify this process. In addition, it has been

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pointed out that the Matthew effect as a social mechanism undermines meritocracy in science as researchers, who have been fortunate to begin with, benefit from self-perpetuating processes of accumulative advantage, while similarly talented but less fortunate early career scholars do not (Bol et al. 2018).

Socioeconomic impact

A core socioeconomic argument for large scale funding is that it directly or indirectly promotes industry-science collaboration and thereby strengthens the impact of research on innovation and international competitiveness (Bonaccorsi and Daraio, 2005; Rogers et al., 2012). Strong research centres located in areas of strategic economic importance can help to direct research towards societal goals and to enhance the quality of research within these areas.

In their study, Bonaccorsi and Daraio (2005) examine whether the creation of large research organisations such as the French National Centre for Scientific Research and the French National Institute of Health and Medical Research enhances scientific productivity. This might be expected due to proximity, i.e. that bigger units facilitate personal interaction, face-to-face communication, transmission of tacit knowledge etc. – or a reduction of costs caused by agglomeration. However, based on a study of the French National Institute of Health and Medical Research in France and Italian National Research Council in Italy, Bonaccorsi and Daraio (2005) do not find evidence supporting the idea that a concentration of resources into larger institutes will lead to an upsurge in scientific productivity. This conclusion is supported by Breschi and Malerba's (2011) findings. Examining the scientific productivity effects of the European Union's 6th framework program, they find that grants and consortia can get too big. According to them, scientific productivity increases up to a certain point when consortia grow in size – beyond this point decreasing marginal returns can be observed.

Epistemic effects

Another line of argumentation identified in the literature is concerned with the epistemic effects of funding policies either targeting 'selectivity' or 'diversity'. Studies that highlight benefits associated with an increase in grant size, point to resource concentration as a way to achieve certain positive epistemic effects (Hellström et al., 2017). For instance, it is assumed that concentration of resources in large centres or units can facilitate research capacity and stimulate scientific development and advances (Hellström et al., 2017). The argument here is that selectivity in the distribution of funding will secure enough resources for the most capable and productive scientists, who also have the greatest potential to produce path-breaking research results (Hicks and Katz, 2011; Bloch and Sørensen, 2015; Aagaard et al., 2020). Another argument for focusing effort through concentration of research funds is that large-scale funding schemes such as centres of excellence allow for resource availability, stability and flexibility to pursue 'high-risk/high-gain research' (Hellström et al., 2017).

On the other hand, if each grantee is seen as an experiment, many grantees will increase the number of experiments and thereby the likelihood of scientific breakthroughs. A funding strategy aimed at selectivity or concentration, i.e. handing out large grants to a smaller number of investigators, is perceived as risky because it reduces the number of experiments (Fortin and Currie, 2013; Bloch and Sørensen, 2015; Aagaard

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et al., 2020). Therefore, one of the most frequent arguments in favour of funding strategies aimed at diversity, is that spreading out smaller grants on a larger number of researchers and thereby supporting a greater number of investigators at moderate funding levels spreads risk and provides better conditions for risk-taking. This again increases the potential for transformative research and the chances of scientific breakthroughs (Lorsch, 2015; Kimble et al., 2015; Aagaard et al., 2020).

Another advantage of diversifying research investments is that making more small and medium-sized grants available to a larger pool of researchers increases the diversity of fields of research and the range of opportunities available to PhD students and researchers (von Tunzelmann et al., 2003; Dimke et al., 2019; Aagaard et al., 2020).

Equity

Resource concentration has an adverse effect on equity in science. Equity can be enhanced by distributing research funds more evenly to "support economic development, strengthen research and enhance diversity and participation in the research enterprise" (Hicks and Katz, 2011, p.143).

On the other hand, if funding distributions are too heavily informed by equity considerations the best researchers might lose incentives for applying (Hicks and Katz, 2011). Along the lines of this argument, decision makers do not dare to match resource allocation with the extremely unequal distribution of research performance due to an inequality aversion inherent in the science system (Hicks and Katz, 2011). Another critique levelled at egalitarian funding schemes is that such practices could lead to the dilution of resources and funding bodies renouncing their control over the course of science (Hicks and Katz, 2011).

Also, gender imbalances in research have received increasing attention, prompting the examination of potential sources of gender bias in peer review and other forms of scientific assessment (Addis 2010; European Commission, 2008). Given that gender imbalances are greatest for the highest academic positions, such as professorships, concerns can be raised that a growing focus on large research initiatives such as centers will exacerbate existing gender inequalities (Sandström et al., 2010; Aksnes et al., 2012; DFG, 2012).

Empirical evidence on grant size and performance

Empirical evidence on the impact of project size for grants is fairly limited, though a larger number of analyses have been conducted that are related to the topic. This includes for example analyses of the role of group size (Von Tunzelmann et al., 2003; Johnston, 1994; University Alliance, 2011; Seglen and Aksnes, 2000), of funding acknowledgements (Rigby and Julian, 2012), of large research centres (Sandström et al., 2010; Aksnes et al., 2012; Rogers et al., 2012; Ida and Fukuzawa, 2013; Bloch et al. 2016), and of total funds per researcher (Ma et al., 2015; Mongeon et al. 2016; Katz and Matter, 2017; Shibayama, 2011).

Several studies have examined the role of large research centres, and while these analyses are relevant to the issue of grant size, they do not provide direct evidence on the relation between grant size and performance (see for instance Sandström et al., 2010; Aksnes et al., 2012; Rogers et al., 2012; Ida and Fukuzawa, 2013; and Bloch et al., 2016).

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A limited number of studies have looked specifically at the relation between grant size and research performance. In some cases, the studies have only measured productivity in terms of number of publications, though most have considered both productivity and some measure of scientific impact, either journal impact, citation impact or the number of highly cited articles. The general result from these studies is that while both the number of publications and citation impact typically increase with grant size, there are decreasing marginal returns. Measured per dollar spent, these few studies generally find that both publications and impact are decreasing in grant size. However, as indicated by the description below, evidence is limited and based on varying methods. These range from analysis based on survey and qualitative interview responses to statistical analysis of the relation between grant size and different output measures.

Among the limited number of analyses that look specifically at the role of size for research grants, an example is an NIH analysis of the scientific productivity of researchers funded by grants from the NIH National Institute of General Medical Sciences (UNIGMS) for 2006 (Wadman, 2010). The statistical analysis compares number publications with grant amounts, finding that the median number of publications was highest for medium sized grants, peaking at around 750,000 USD. However, in terms of publications per dollar spent, the smallest grants at around 250,000 USD had the highest productivity. The analysis, however, does not look into other performance measures such as citation impacts, nor does it account for factors such as experience, discipline or prior funding.

Two other studies, the first for the NSF and the second for the Danish Council for Independent Research, look in more detail at the role of size for project grants. The NSF commissioned a study on precisely this topic, on principal investigators' (PI) perceptions concerning grant size and duration. The study relies solely on a survey of PIs perceptions and thus did not measure impact on scientific productivity (Ballou et al. 2002). The study covered all PIs for the fiscal year 2001 (in all 4,989). Grant sizes were small to medium sized, with roughly a third each under 162,000 USD, between 162,000-330,000 USD, and over 330,000 USD. Respondents noted limitations due to both amount and length, citing time spent writing proposals and lack of continuity as key reasons why grant size and duration should be increased. However, taking funding constraints into consideration, there is a trade-off between size and success rates, i.e., the larger the grants, the lesser the number of researchers that can receive them. If forced to choose between increasing the amount only, the duration only, or the number of awards, 40% of PIs chose amounts, 24% length and the remaining 36% the number of awards.

A study of grants from the Danish Council for Independent Research covered project grants of a similar size as those for NSF, focusing on a broad range of impacts, both qualitative and quantitative (Bloch et al., 2011; Bloch et al., 2014). Bibliometric analysis on a matched sample of PIs and rejected applicants indicated that PIs for larger projects (over 160,000 USD) had both a higher number of publications and citation rates before and after the grant period, and also a larger increase in productivity over the period. In contrast, survey responses on the number of publications for projects as a whole, suggested that the average number of peer-reviewed articles per 100,000 USD granted was substantially higher for small projects (under 160,000 USD), more than double that for larger projects in four out of five main fields. It was not possible to confirm this result via funding acknowledgements or project reporting. Smaller grants were predominantly awarded to early career researchers, who according to interviews with them were used to kick-start their careers and establish them in academia (Degn et al., 2011). The increase in number of publications from these grants was therefore not related to smaller grants benefitting from work previously carried out on bigger grants.

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Similar to developments in Denmark, Fortin and Currie (2013) note a shift in funding practice at the National Science and Engineering Research Center (NSERC) in Canada from awarding a large number of small grants to a focus on a smaller number of large grants. Motivated by this change, they use regression analysis to examine the relation between grant size and four indicators across different disciplines: number of publications, number of citations, most cited articles and number of highly cited articles. For all four measures, they find that performance is increasing with grant size, but with diminishing returns, particularly for impact. Hence, the authors find that both publications and citations per dollar funded are decreasing with grant size.

Danthi et al. (2014) compare NIH grants that were allocated as part of the regular budget (“de novo R01 grants”) of the NIH with grants that were distributed through the same program, but through funding provided by the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act (ARRA). ARRA-funded grants were from the same NIH program, but were smaller, of a shorter duration and had fared less well in peer review (i.e., they would not have received funding without the additional ARRA funds). Hence, this offers both an opportunity to examine the role of grant size through statistical comparison of the two grants and the effectiveness of peer review in selecting the best projects. Citation impact for each grant was normalized by subject, article type and year of publication. Multivariable linear regression models controlled for a number of factors, including peer-review grant percentile ranking, grant size, project duration, involvement of vertebrate animals and human research subjects, and performance of a clinical trial, early-stage/new-investigator status, prior NIH funding, and number of prior NIH grants. The study finds that the number of articles and impact per dollar awarded was comparable for the two groups of grants.

Lauer et al. (2015) analyses the bibliometric outcomes of de novo cardiovascular R01 grants funded by the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute of the NIH (NHLBI) between 1980 and 2011. The authors find that the number of top 10% highly cited articles per million USD is increasing in award size, but the coefficient of this increase is much less than 1.

The National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) made a significant change in their funding practices, with large increases in both the size and duration of its grants. Increases varied across fields, for example with 70% increases in average grant size within Chemistry but much smaller increases within the Medical Sciences. Hu (2020) examines the effects of this change on several performance indicators (number of publications, Journal impact weighted publications, number of citations and highest journal impact of publications), controlling for factors such as field, affiliation, age and number of previous grants. Hu (2020) finds large positive effects for the number of publications but smaller effects for impact. However, even for publications, it is unclear whether the results imply increasing or decreasing returns to grant size. Furthermore, Hu (2020) finds that effects are by far the largest for first-time grantees or for researchers with a single previous grant, and smaller or even negative for multiple grant holders.

Conclusion

In this chapter, we have examined the role of size for research funding grants, both recent trends and the potential implications of increases in grant size. This study is motivated by a number of indications of increased concentration of research funding, and also by cases of significant increases in average grant sizes in the last twenty years, such as in Denmark. These trends are, however, not present in all cases, with a

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number of examples of countries or funding organisations where the average size of project grants has remained relatively constant in real terms. It would be interesting to take advantage of this variation to examine whether increases in grant size have improved outcomes in those funding organisations where such changes have taken place.

Above, we also explored arguments for and against increasing the size of grants, placed under seven interrelated categories: *Efficiency/Productivity*, *Administration*, *Excellence*, *Matthew effects*, *Epistemic effects*, *Socioeconomic impact*, and *Equity*. Efficiency or productivity-related arguments centre around ideas that a critical mass in terms of project size is needed to achieve scientific excellence and that advantages can be reaped in terms of economies of scale to research. Administrative costs are argued to make small grants too costly, though on the other hand, very large grants can require great effort to coordinate and administer.

Excellence arguments focus both on the rationale that the best researchers should have ample funding in order to achieve scientific breakthroughs, and that large grants are more likely to produce novel results. Parallel arguments are made for socioeconomic impacts, namely that large grants are more likely to produce advances that can foster innovation. Large grants are argued to intensify Matthew effects, i.e., the concentration of resources among a smaller group of successful scientists. This has both been argued to be positive as an allocation mechanism, and negative as it reinforces unequal distributions of research funding – short term as well as long term.

Grant size has also been linked to epistemic effects, where large grants can be seen as better facilitating epistemic changes in research approaches. However, concentration of funding is also argued to reduce diversity in research. The peer review process has been shown to be imperfect in identifying the most promising projects and also to be subject to a number of biases, both of which can be seen as arguments for greater spreading of funding in smaller grants. Resource concentration has an adverse effect on equity in science, which can be argued to have detrimental repercussions for the science system as a whole.

Empirical analysis of the relation between grant size and research outcomes is somewhat limited. However, existing empirical evidence suggests that there are diminishing returns to grant size, measured for example in terms of number of publications, citation impact and number of highly cited papers. Basic statistical analysis comparing grant size with research outcomes shows a fairly clear pattern of decreasing returns, and qualitative interviews illustrate in particular the importance of small grants for early career researchers. However, less work has been done to control for factors that are related to research outcomes, such as research experience and prior funding and performance.

While a number of positive potential implications of increasing the size of research grants can be found, there may also be a number of adverse effects. Given this, in our view, the lack of evidence that supports positive benefits of a strong shift to larger grants and the increasing inequality in science raises questions on the merits of increased grant size. This issue should also be seen in the context of a science system with increasing competition and a growing number of early career researchers in temporary positions. Increased concentration can be seen both as a result of funding policies and as a factor that increases tensions. Efforts to restrict the number of grants per researcher, to offer smaller size grants or lotteries to reduce costs and mediate peer review biases can help to counter these developments (Adam, 2019; Fang and Casadevall, 2016; Vaesen and Katzav, 2017). In addition, more knowledge is needed both on the relation between grant size and other funding characteristics and research outcomes, and on the consequences of changes in funding landscapes for research conditions and research careers at a systemic level.

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References

Aagaard, K. Kladakis, A. and M. W. Nielsen, Concentration or dispersal of research funding? *Quantitative Sci. Studies* 1, 117–149 (2020).

Adam, D. (2019). Science funders gamble on grant lotteries. *Nature*, 575(7785), 574-5.

Addis, E. (2010) Meta-analysis of gender and science research: Topic report - Gender and Scientific Excellence. www.genderandscience.org.

Aksnes D., Benner, M., Borlaug, S.B., Hansen, H.F., Kallerud, E., Kristiansen, E., Langfeldt, L., Pelkonen, A. and Sivertsen, G. (2012) 'Centres of Excellence in the Nordic countries'. NIFU Working Paper 4/2012.

Alberts, B. M. 1985. Limits to growth: in biology, small science is good science. *Cell*, 41(2), 337–338. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0092-8674\(85\)80001-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0092-8674(85)80001-5)

Alberts, B., Kirschner, M. W., Tilghman, S., & Varmus, H. 2014. Rescuing US biomedical research from its systemic flaws. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(16), 5773–5777. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1404402111>

Arora-Jonsson, S., Brunsson, N. and Edlund, P. (2022). "The Construction of Competition in Public Research Funding Systems". Forthcoming in Eds. Lepori, Jongbloed & Hicks, *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar. Ballou, J., Mishkind, M., Mooney, G. and van Kammen, W. 2002 National Science Foundation Report on Efficiency of Grant Size and Duration. Arlington: National Science Foundation.

Ballou, J., Mishkind, M., Mooney, G., & van Kammen, W. (2002). National science foundation report on efficiency of grant size and duration. National Science Foundation, Chief Budget and Systems, Operations and Budget Branch, Arlington, VA.

Berg, J. M. 2012. Well-funded investigators should receive extra scrutiny. *Nature*, 489(7415), 203–203. <https://doi.org/10.1038/489203a>

Bloch, C., Schneider, J.W., Sinkjær, T., 2016. Size, Accumulation and Performance for Research Grants: Examining the Role of Size for Centres of Excellence. *PLoS One* 11, e0147726. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0147726>

Bloch, C. and Sørensen, M.P., 2015. The size of research funding: Trends and implications. *Sci. Public Policy* 42, 30–43. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scu019>

Bloch, C., Sørensen, M.P. and Ravn, T., 2011. Evaluation of Research Project Grants of the Danish Council for Independent Research - Main report. Copenhagen: Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation. (in Danish).

Bloch, C., Sørensen, M. P., Graversen, E. K., Schneider, J. W., Schmidt, E. K., Aagaard, K., & Mejlgaard, N., 2014. Developing a methodology to assess the impact of research grant funding: A mixed methods approach. *Evaluation and program planning*, 43, 105-117.

Bol, T., de Vaan, M., & van de Rijt, A. 2018. The Matthew effect in science funding. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(19), 4887–4890. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1719557115>

- Bloch et al. (2022) "Size matters! On the implications of increasing the size of research grants", in: Lepori B., Jongbloed B. & Hicks D., *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar Publishing, forthcoming in 2023.
- Bollen, J., Crandall, D., Junk, D., Ding, Y., & Börner, K. 2014. From funding agencies to scientific agency. *EMBO Reports*, 15(2), 131–133. <https://doi.org/10.1002/embr.201338068>
- Bonaccorsi, A. and Daraio, C., 2005. Exploring size and agglomeration effects on public research productivity. *Scientometrics* 63, 87–120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-005-0205-3>
- Breschi, S. and Malerba, F., 2011. Assessing the scientific and technological output of EU Framework 16 Programmes: evidence from the FP6 projects in the ICT field. *Scientometrics* 88, 239–257. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-011-0378-x>
- Cole, J. R. and S. Cole, *Social Stratification in Science* (University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1973).
- Danthi, N., Wu, C. O., Shi, P., & Lauer, M. (2014). Percentile ranking and citation impact of a large cohort of National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute–funded cardiovascular R01 grants. *Circulation research*, 114(4), 600-606.
- Degn, L., Faber, S. T., & Ravn, T. (2011). Delrapport 3: Case-/interviewundersøgelsen, Evaluering af virkemidlet forskningsprojekter [Sub-report 3: Case and Interview study for the Evaluation of the instrument Research projects]. Danish Centre for Studies in Research and Research Policy, Aarhus University: <https://ufm.dk/publikationer/2011/filer-2011/3-interviewundersoegelsen.pdf>
- DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft/German Research Foundation) (2003) Funding Ranking 2003. Institutions – Regions – Networks. DFG Approvals and Other Basic Data on Publicly Funded Research. Bonn: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft: http://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/dfg_im_profil/evaluation_statistik/ranking/archiv/dfg_funding_ranking_2003.pdf
- DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft/German Research Foundation)). (2012) Förderatlas 2012. Kennzahlen zur öffentlich finanzierten Forschung in Deutschland. Bonn: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft: http://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/dfg_im_profil/evaluation_statistik/foerderatlas/dfg-foerderatlas_2012.pdf
- DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft/German Research Foundation) (2013) DFG Video Portal on the Excellence Initiative: <http://www.excellence-initiative.com/excellence-initiative>.
- Dimke, H., Norn, M. T., Christiansen, P. M., Wohlert, J., and Zinner, N. T. 2019. Most scientists prefer small and mid-sized research grants. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 3:765-767.
- Doyle, J. M., Quinn, K., Bodenstein, Y. A., Wu, C. O., Danthi, N., & Lauer, M. S. 2015. Association of percentile ranking with citation impact and productivity in a large cohort of de novo NIMH-funded R01 grants. *Molecular Psychiatry*, 20(9), 1030–1036. <https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2015.71>
- European Commission (2008) *The Gender Challenge in Research Funding. Assessing the European National Scenes*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
- Fang, F. C., & Casadevall, A. 2016. Research Funding: the Case for a Modified Lottery. *MBio*, 7(2), e00422-16. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00422-16>
- Fortin, J.-M., & Currie, D. J. 2013. Big Science vs. Little Science: How Scientific Impact Scales with Funding. *PLoS ONE*, 8(6), e65263. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0065263>

- Bloch et al. (2022) "Size matters! On the implications of increasing the size of research grants", in: Lepori B., Jongbloed B. & Hicks D., *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar Publishing, forthcoming in 2023.
- Franssen, T. & De Rijcke, S. 2019. "The rise of project funding and its effects on the social structure of academia". In: Cannizzo, F & Osbaldiston, N. (Eds) *The social structures of global academia*. London: Routledge.
- Gordon, R., & Poulin, B. J. 2009a. Cost of the NSERC Science Grant Peer Review System Exceeds the Cost of Giving Every Qualified Researcher a Baseline Grant. *Accountability in Research*, 16(1), 13–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989620802689821>
- Gordon, R., & Poulin, B. J. 2009b. Indeed: Cost of the NSERC Science Grant Peer Review System Exceeds the Cost of Giving Every Qualified Researcher a Baseline Grant. *Accountability in Research*, 16(4), 232–233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989620903065590>
- Hellström, T., Jabrane, L., and Brattström, E., 2017. Center of excellence funding: Connecting organizational capacities and epistemic effects. *Res. Eval.* 27, 73–81. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvx043>
- Hicks, D., & Katz, J. S. 2011. Equity and Excellence in Research Funding. *Minerva*, Vol. 49, pp. 137–151. <https://doi.org/10.2307/43548599> Hicks, D. and Katz, J.S. (2011) Equity and excellence in research funding, *Minerva*, 49(2):137-151.
- Hu, A. G. (2020). Public funding and the ascent of Chinese science: Evidence from the National Natural Science Foundation of China. *Research Policy*, 49(5), 103983.
- Ida, T., & Fukuzawa, N. 2013. Effects of large-scale research funding programs: a Japanese case study. *Scientometrics*, 94(3), 1253–1273. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-012-0841-3>
- Johnston, R. 1994. Effects of resource concentration on research performance. *Higher Education*, 28(1), 25–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01383570>
- Johnston, R., Grigg, L. & Currie, J. 1995. Size versus Performance in Research. *Australian Universities' Review*, 60–64. <https://doi.org/https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ523114>
- Katz, Y., & Matter, U. (2017). On the biomedical elite: Inequality and stasis in scientific knowledge production. *Berkman Klein Center Research Publication*, (2017-5).
- Katz, Yarden, and Matter, Ullrich. 2020. Metrics of Inequality: The Concentration of Resources in the U.S. Biomedical Elite. *Science as Culture*, 29(4):475-502. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09505431.2019.1694882>
- Kenna, R., & Berche, B. 2011. Critical mass and the dependency of research quality on group size. *Scientometrics*, 86(2), 527–540. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-010-0282-9>
- Kimble, J., Bement, W. M., Chang, Q., Cox, B. L., Drinkwater, N. R., Gourse, R. L., ... Seidel, H. S. 2015. Strategies from UW-Madison for rescuing biomedical research in the US. *ELife*, 4, e09305. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.09305>
- Laudel, G. (2022). "Researchers' responses to their funding situation"., in Lepori B., Jongbloed B., Hicks D., *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar, forthcoming in 2022.
- Lauer, M. S., Danthi, N. S., Kaltman, J., & Wu, C. (2015). Predicting productivity returns on investment: thirty years of peer review, grant funding, and publication of highly cited papers at the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute. *Circulation research*, 117(3), 239-243.

- Bloch et al. (2022) "Size matters! On the implications of increasing the size of research grants", in: Lepori B., Jongbloed B. & Hicks D., *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar Publishing, forthcoming in 2023.
- Larivière, V., Macaluso, B., Archambault, É., & Gingras, Y. (2010). Which scientific elites? On the concentration of research funds, publications and citations. *Research Evaluation*, 19(1), 45-53.
- Lorsch, J. R. 2015. Maximizing the return on taxpayers' investments in fundamental biomedical research. *Molecular Biology of the Cell*, 26(9), 1578–1582. <https://doi.org/10.1091/mbc.e14-06-1163>
- Ma, A., Mondragón, R. J., & Latora, V. (2015). Anatomy of funded research in science. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(48), 14760-14765.
- Madsen, E. B., & Aagaard, K. (2020). Concentration of Danish research funding on individual researchers and research topics: Patterns and potential drivers. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(3), 1159-1181.
- Melkers, J. and Kreth, Q. (2022). "Research Funding and Careers: Individual and Contextual Factors", in Lepori B., Jongbloed B., Hicks D., *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar, forthcoming in 2022.
- Merton, R.K. (1968) 'The Matthew Effect in science', *Science* 159(3810): 56-63.
- Mongeon, P., Brodeur, C., Beaudry, C., & Larivière, V. 2016. Concentration of research funding leads to decreasing marginal returns. *Research Evaluation*, 25(4), rvw007. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvw007>
- Murray, D. L., Morris, D., Lavoie, C., Leavitt, P. R., MacIsaac, H., Masson, M. E. J., and Villard, M-A. 2016. Bias in Research Grant Evaluation Has Dire Consequences for Small Universities. *PLoS ONE* 11(6): e0155876. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0155876>
- Nag, S., Yang, H., Buccola, S., & Ervin, D. 2013. Productivity and financial support in academic bioscience. *Applied Economics*, 45(19), 2817–2826. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2012.676737>
- Narin, F., Stevens, K. and Whitlow, E.S. (1991) 'Scientific co-operation in Europe and the citation of multinationally authored papers', *Scientometrics*, 21, 313-323.
- National Science Foundation (NSF) (2007) Impact of Proposal and Award Management Mechanisms. Final Report, NSF 07-45, August 1, 2007.
- Nielsen, M. W., & Andersen, J. P. (2021). Global citation inequality is on the rise. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(7). Petersen, A.M. and O. Penner (2014). Inequality and cumulative advantage in science careers: A case study of high-impact journals. *EPJ Data Sci.* 3, 1–25.
- Reale, E., Gulbrandsen, M. and Scherngell, T. (2022). "R&D Programs as Instruments for Governmental R&D Funding Policy", in Lepori B., Jongbloed B., Hicks D., *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar, forthcoming in 2022.
- Rigby, J. and Julian, K. 2014. On the horns of a dilemma: does more funding for research lead to more research or a waste of resources that calls for optimization of researcher portfolios? An analysis using funding acknowledgement data. *Scientometrics*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-014-1259-x>
- Rogers, J., Youtie, J. and Luciano, K. (2012) 'Program-level assessment of research centers: Contribution of Nanoscale Science and Engineering Centers to US Nanotechnology National Initiative goals', *Research Evaluation*, 21, 368-380.
- Sandström, U., Wold, A., Jordansson, B., Ohlsson, B. and Smedberg, Å. (2010) Hans Excellens: om miljardsatsningarna på starka forskningsmiljöer. Stockholm.

- Bloch et al. (2022) "Size matters! On the implications of increasing the size of research grants", in: Lepori B., Jongbloed B. & Hicks D., *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar Publishing, forthcoming in 2023.
- Seglen, P.O. and Aksnes, D.W. (2000) 'Scientific productivity and group size: A bibliometric analysis of Norwegian microbiological research', *Scientometrics* 49(1): 125-143.
- Shibayama, S. (2011). Distribution of academic research funds: a case of Japanese national research grant. *Scientometrics*, 88(1), 43-60.
- Sousa, R. 2008. Research funding: less should be more. *Science* (New York, N.Y.), 322(5906), 1324–1325. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.322.5906.1324b>
- Stephan, P. (1996) 'The Economics of Science', *Journal of Economic Literature* 34: 1199-1235.
- Sörlin, S. (2007) 'Funding Diversity: Performance-based Funding Regimes as Drivers of Differentiation in Higher Education Systems', *Higher Education Policy* 20: 413-440.
- Sørensen, M.P., Bloch, C. and Young, M. (2016). Excellence in the knowledge-based economy: from scientific to research excellence. *European Journal of Higher Education* 6(3), 217-236.
- Thomas, D. and Ramos-Vielba, I. (2022). "Reframing study of research(er) funding: From single funding instruments to configurations, trails and amalgamations", in Lepori B., Jongbloed B., Hicks D., *Handbook of Public Research Funding*, Edward Elgar, forthcoming in 2022.
- University Alliance (2011) Funding research excellence: research group size, critical mass and performance. Report prepared by Evidence. London: University Alliance.
- Vaesen K, Katzav J (2017) How much would each researcher receive if competitive government research funding were distributed equally among researchers? *PLoS ONE* 12(9): e0183967. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0183967>
- von Tunzelmann, N., Ranga, M., Martin, B. and Geuna, A. (2003) The Effects of Size on Research Performance: A SPRU Review. Report prepared for the Office of Science and Technology, Department of Trade and Industry.
- Wadman, M. (2010) 'Study says middle sized labs do best', *Nature* 468: 356-357.
- Wahls, W. P. 2018a. High cost of bias: Diminishing marginal returns on NIH grant funding to institutions. <https://doi.org/10.1101/367847>
- Wahls, W. P. 2018b. The NIH must reduce disparities in funding to maximize its return on investments from taxpayers. *eLife*; 7:e34965. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.34965>
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- ⁱ <https://www.forskningsradet.no/en/statistics-and-evaluations/statistics-and-evaluations/the--research-councils-statistics/> (accessed 08/05/21) Total inflation for the entire period was 21%.
- ⁱⁱ <https://data.snf.ch/key-figures> (accessed 11/05/21). Overall inflation for the entire period was 2.2%.
- ⁱⁱⁱ https://www.nsf.gov/about/budget/fy2020/pdf/04_fy2020.pdf (accessed 08/05/21)
- ^{iv} https://reporter.nih.gov/search/_KEMtbKkc0iOZVjjoNilFw/projects/chart (accessed 08/05/21)
- ^v <https://report.nih.gov/fundingfacts/fundingfacts.aspx> (accessed 11/05/21)
- ^{vi} <https://rms.arc.gov.au/RMS/Report/Download/Report/a3f6be6e-33f7-4fb5-98a6-7526aaa184cf/218>
<https://www.transparency.gov.au/annual-reports/australian-research-council/reporting-year/2018-2019-38> (both accessed 11/05/21)
- ^{vii} https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/dfg_im_profil/geschaefsstelle/publikationen/dfg_jb2019.pdf (p. 198) (accessed 11/05/21)